

SOCIAL COMMUNICATION STUDIES

AN OVERVIEW ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ADVERTISING IN EGYPT, THE UK, AND BELARUS

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Abstract

This article is meant to provide some initial notions, materials, and concept for the study of advertising. It draws on advertising literature in three countries Egypt, the UK, and Belarus. I committed to bridging the gap between the huge body of research on advertising in the three countries. The history of advertising is particularly explained in these three countries briefly. We need to understand how advertising was formed and legalized in these countries in order to arm ourselves with knowledge about practical, historical, and legal forms of advertising. In this article I wanted to answer the question who invented the art of advertising? How is advertising shaped in Egypt, the UK, and Belarus, historically, legally, and literary? Advertising has an impact on our lives, our perspectives, and feelings. This article aims to provide researchers with some knowledge about the development of the advertising processes to imagine and understand the amount of devolvement was achieved and investigate this field of advertising as well as how it influences and shapes our social lives.

Materials and Methods: The study is based on publications by Arabic, English and Belarusian authors, which highlight on advertising, its history, and its literature. General scientific and special research methods were used in the course of the study.

Findings and Discussions: After studying the scientific works presented in the article, the author identified the issues that are raised in these scientific studies, such as the initial of the advertising and special attention paid to the development of advertising in these three countries and its various characteristics and approaches.

Keywords: Advertising, giant billboards, advertisers, Egyptian advertising, British advertising agencies, Belarus advertising.

Who invented the art of advertising?

The Pharaohs, not the Romans, were the first to invent the art of advertising, it was posted by Dr. M. Al-Sabban. In a thesis on which he was awarded a doctorate, Dr. M. Al-Sabban, (Professor of Design and Advertising at the Faculty of Specific Education at Cairo University) proved scientifically that the Pharaohs were the first

to invent the art of advertising, thus smashing old theories that traced the creation of the foundations of this art to the Greeks and Romans. Through his study, it became clear to him that the ancient Egyptian letters are not symbols as it is well known, but rather forms equivalent to the alphabets, which are closer to forms of nature. During his research, he stopped at the studies that indicated that the Greeks and Romans were the first to invent the art of advertising, so he started working to verify the truth of the matter until he ended up proving that the Pharaohs were the first to know this art in the world. One of the main difficulties he faced was the lack of a reference for the art of advertising with the Pharaohs, which forced him to research, and read about aspects of ancient Egyptian life. In addition to the presence of thousands of artifacts to be studied and the translations of ancient Egyptian writings contained in them to monitor the dimensions of ancient Egyptian thought. Advertising is related to reading and writing. The ancient Egyptians were educated enough to create written advertising messages in various aspects of life that differ from the current vision of commercial advertising. By studying texts, monitoring the events of their daily lives, it became clear the Pharaohs had an innovative advertising vision. For example, it was written on the door of one of the tombs "O living people passing

in front of this place, do not enter it with the intention of distorting it, otherwise the crocodile will wrap around you" which is a clear warning to anyone who dares to tamper with the cemetery Its contents are very similar to signs that we find in public places, such as "No Smoking" and "Danger of Entry" [1].

In her article on Egyptian civilization, "Political Propaganda in Ancient Egypt," N. M. Ahmed asserted that political propaganda in ancient Egypt was the goal and means for anyone who wanted to reach an important political or religious position, meaning that he was seeking to include the largest number of popular support for him by announcing his work or by proving his eligibility for the position, whether through the job order or as a son of a dynasty that monopolized the position [2]. From the previous examples, we can be sure that the pharaohs were the first people on earth who used the art of advertising in order to persuade, warn, or sell something, or an idea.

Tej K. Bhatia in his book, Advertising in rural India (in 2000), highlighted in his study on how pharaohs wrote on special type of papers they called it papyrus which was used by the Egyptians to create posters, letters, and /or to write a notice about lost property. Another example of ancient advertising is wall or rock painting for advertisements, which is still practiced today in many regions.

We pay attention to the tools or means of advertising in old ages. Moreover we would better call them the stages of the improving of advertisements, so papyrus was the first means of advertising, then David Wengrow in his article, Prehistories of Commodity Branding (2008), indicates that about 4000 years ago people started using seals and tags made of stones. In ancient

times, many products were marked with seals or tags. Affixing simple stone seals to goods dates back to around 4,000 years ago; over time, these seals evolved into clay ones with exquisite images, frequently representing the producer's identity. After a long time people started using some maker marks that is around 1300 BC. Then came the Indians, they applied distinguished marks to valuable goods such as precious metals [3].

Advertising in Egypt

Early nineteenth-century advertisements were cliched and longwinded. However, they continue to be primarily factual and informational in nature. As one might anticipate from an official newspaper, many of the advertisements are for items that the government wants to sell, like surplus goods or stock in its corporations. Additionally, there are advertisements placed by people looking to sell their homes, properties, and books. The majority adheres to a formula in which they outline what is being sold, buyers should get in touch with by a certain date, and state that the item will be sold to the highest bidder. These advertisements were targeted at middle-class and upper-class males who were interested in staying current with the state of the economy. The quantity, frequency, and sophistication of advertisements all increased as more publishers realized the value of using advertising. At the same time, there were an increasing number of businesses, outlets, goods, and services looking for advertising. Then, the first significant boom appeared in the market for patented drugs and cosmetics; however, they were different from English advertisements in that they occasionally mentioned a specific pharmacy. Advertisements blurred the lines between foods, beverages, and even the distinction between food and beauty, telling consumers that they could add vitamins to their hair to restore its beauty and drink wine to increase their vitality. Advertising that was focused specifically on one gender was rare, despite the fact that many ads clearly targeted women. The biggest distinction was the absence of official notices. Then, commercials got fancier, more elaborately decorated, used different fonts, and had better, more frequent sketches as illustrations. Additionally, there was more gender specificity, and they reflected the growth of the middle class and of foreign corporations. Traditional advertising, however, continued to be prevalent during the study period. The indication of a middle class that is expanding and becoming more affluent. The rise in hotel and vacation advertising is one piece of the puzzle in this case. In the past, guidebooks and the foreign press were the main places to find hotel advertisements. The most opulent hotels with a wide range of amenities and services were frequently featured in these advertisements. On rare occasions, advertisements for these upscale hotels would also appear in Arabic periodicals. Advertisements for hotels start to appeal to more modest people. Egypt has become a more significant economic and political force in international affairs. The 1952 Revolution that put Nasser in power, the 1956 Suez Canal nationalization, the 1958 Soviet Union support for the High Dam, and the 1958 union with Syria are all evidence of Egypt's burgeoning vitality. The Egyptian press under-

went major developments, especially the introduction of illustrated magazines, and a significant increase in the number and quality of advertisements [4]. Due to the departure of numerous foreigners (Greek, and Italians etc...), who were significant traders, Egypt's distribution system has undergone a significant change over the past few years. However, there is some debate regarding the worth of the services provided in a developing nation by these trader middlemen. The importance of retail advertising and promotion is minimal. Less than 20% of newspaper advertisements are for retail. The cost of retail advertising is prohibitive for the majority of retailers due to the lack of local news publications, all significant magazines and newspapers are regional. Some department stores make extensive use of circulars to advertise clearance sales. Rarely is direct mail used. Government price controls, the live-and-let-live philosophy, the idea of a limited market, and the maintenance of resale prices are the foundations of retail price policies. Retailers typically don't think that decreasing prices will result in more sales; instead, they aim to make the highest possible gross profit on each transaction. Few retailers are aware of the value of turnover and the idea of maximizing profits by selling a large volume of goods at low prices. Price reductions intended to boost sales at the expense of rivals are typically thought to be unfair. Additionally, many implicit price agreements are in place to prevent price competition among retailers who handle related product lines.

Because of the country's efforts to industrialize, the lack of adequate internal transportation and storage infrastructure, the prevalence of small manufacturers, and the concentration of manufacturing in Cairo and Alexandria, efficient wholesaling facilities are crucial in Egypt. Whole-sellers have traditionally held a privileged position in the marketing of goods in Egypt. When acting as import wholesalers, wholesalers were frequently able to prevent local products from entering the market.

Currently, Giant billboards, endless television advertisements become a staple part of daily life in Cairo. Advertising has always played essential role in Egyptian society, although it has risen in importance and appearance in recent years. The 1970's saw a rise in the use of consumer insights and humor as key selling points in shaping advertisements as a form of entertainment. The innovation in the use of culturally relevant humor evolved into the creation, use and adaptation of advertisement jingles during the 1980's. During the 1990's, Egyptian advertisements, the use of billboards became more popular, advertising major reliance on beauty and feminine appeal, in addition to satire, humor and dramatic plot.

More recently, companies made use of the current rap and trap. Egypt's approach to advertising is still slightly outdated when compared to the rest of the world, mainly due to the fact that we still need to cater to what would be most relevant to and accepted by our society.

Advertising now, even with the added role of the digital medium, it seems as though TV ads and video production are still the leading advertising options for

clients and Egypt's general population. These days, advertising agencies have grown in number and there are different advertising giants leading the field than the days of Tarek Nour's reign. Of such agencies are FP7 Cairo, part of McCann World group etc. It seems as though celebrity and concept-driven video advertisements still play a large role in Egypt's advertising today. That being said, advertising has undoubtedly come a long way – it is just a matter of how the world changes around us that will determine how and where we will go from here.

Advertising in the UK

City heralds: In the urban area, people were not well-educated, heralds were authorized to broadcast advertisements and news. Afterwards people began to hire public callers to act as guides [5]. At the same time, street vendors developed a system made up of street runners in order to market their products [6]. Before the emergence of the mass media, these street performers rendered an important public service [7].

Commercial signage has been used for a very long time. Promotional boards and retail banners appear to have emerged independently in the East. Ancient Egyptians were known to use banners to advertise market days and storefronts. Pub owners in medieval Britain were required to erect boards. In the Middle Ages, paintings were used in a variety of commercial settings. The trade card, wall-mounted posters, and, to a lesser extent, small display ads in newspapers, were the three primary forms of advertising in the UK during the 18th century [8]. A popular form of advertising was trade cards. A single product was described on a tiny printed and illustrated card that merchants and tradespeople distributed to customers. The intention was for them to share it with their friends and family. Since agencies were established in the middle of the 19th century, when they primarily used newspapers and magazines, advertising has grown significantly in the UK. London continues to be one of the most significant advertising hubs in the world even though domestic British agencies were swallowed up and transformed into branches of global corporations in the late 19th century [9].

Midway through the 19th century, advertising started to play a significant role in capitalist economies, relying mainly on journals and papers. With the advent of new media like TV, online platform, and portable electronics in the 21st century, ads expanded quickly.

There were concerns about the "Americanization" of British culture and business due to the influx of millions of American soldiers into Britain during the Second World War. The Marshall Plan made it clear that British industry needed to improve its marketing and management capabilities. The advertising firm JWT London was owned and operated by J. W. Thompson in New York City. JWT London held back from advocating strongly for American design. Instead, it uses subtly persuasive techniques, giving up its uniquely American identity in favor of the understated British style.

T. J. Barratt used the Pears brand as an advertising gimmick because of its high culture and quality. Most notably, he used John Everett Millais' painting *Bubbles* as an advertisement by placing a bar of Pears soap in

the foreground. Barratt continued this theme by associating pears with domestic comfort and aspirations of high society in a series of commercials that featured well-groomed middle-class children. Many of the fundamental concepts that form the cornerstone of effective advertising were first proposed by Barratt, and at the time they were widely accepted.

He pointed out the value of building a strong and exclusive brand image for Pears and highlighting the product's accessibility through saturation campaigns on numerous occasions. He claimed that as tastes and fashions change, the advertiser must adapt. Barratt introduced many of the fundamental ideas that form the basis of successful advertising, and they were widely embraced at the time. He repeatedly emphasized the importance of creating a powerful and specific brand image for Pears and emphasizing the product's accessibility through saturation campaigns. He understood the importance of routinely reevaluating the market for changing preferences and norms when he said that tastes change, styles change, and the advertiser has to adjust with them. An idea that was successful a couple of generations ago would now be outmoded, uncompetitive, and unelectable. The contemporary concept may not always be better than the traditional concept, but it is unique and speaks to contemporary tastes [10].

Due to the new functions that the Internet and smartphones now play, significant changes have recently occurred. Advertising must be truthful and accurate in describing the product or service, as well as ethical, moral, and morally righteous. What advertisers can and cannot do is constrained by laws. You must abide by two advertising codes of practice in addition to the laws if you want to advertise legally. Your product or service must be accurately described [11]. The advertising industry has evolved over time in response to societal and media changes. The system is still being developed based on the guiding principles that advertisements shouldn't deceive, hurt, or offend. The ASA and Ofcom entered into a co-regulatory partnership in December 2009 to regulate the advertisements that accompany video-on-demand services in response to the UK Government's decision that new regulations pertaining to VOD services should be delivered under a co-regulatory framework. Before airing, the vast majority of TV and radio advertisements have already been approved. Additionally, since the industry is committed to effective self-regulation, any advertisements that violate the Codes can be quickly pulled without resorting to legal action. However, if necessary, the ASA can impose penalties to get troublesome advertisers in line [12].

Advertising in Belarus

In Belarus, advertising mainly represents are public interests. However, abroad social advertising is used in full force by non-commercial and commercial enterprises. For example, commercial organizations use social advertising to improve their image. Some commercial organizations place public service announcements for charitable purposes as part of their advertising campaigns. The success of social advertising in Belarus is controversial, so how much of the social advertising relates to politics. In foreign countries, children, family

relationships, hunger in third world countries, refugees and the environment get the advantage in the rating of social advertising. Advertisements organizations with a Belarusian base advertise in Belarus. The state owned for-profit corporations run television, magazines, journals, and newspapers, which rely on advertising, subscription fees, and other sales-related income. Freedom of speech is guaranteed by the Belarusian Constitution. The legal framework for advertising in Belarus is subject to the constitution, media law, international obligations and international treaties. By February 2010, all mass media in Belarus had to be registered under the country's new media law. The Belarusian Ministry of Information, which was established in 2001, monitors the nation's media.

In order to coordinate the interaction of state management, public associations, and other organizations producing mass information, enforce mass-media laws, and provide legal advice, the government established a Public Coordination Council for Mass Information by the beginning of 2009. According to Article 1 of the Mass Media Law, journalists and advertisers receives press credentials by the authorities in order to cover both internal and external event are organized by government agencies or non-governmental organizations, which is normal by most of the countries all over the world. Advertising agencies in Belarus penetrate into people's thoughts and feelings. Designers work on creating an image to visualize the idea and make the advertising effective, while copywriters come up with catchy slogans and texts.

Advertising is specifically created by marketing firms in Belarus for the brand and its target market. Therefore, it is best to consult experts if you want to grab the interest of potential customers. Given that everyone in Belarus uses the Internet, internet advertising is a quick way to draw clients. The Internet offers a variety of advertising options that are available 24/7 for business growth. Online advertising, in contrast to conventional forms of promotion, enables you to monitor consumer behavior and responses and quickly adapt to changes in demand and target audience behavior. Targeting advertising consists of a text ad with an eye-catching image. This type of online advertising is used increase brand awareness, to spread information about events, and market local products. Contextual advertising is a message or a text frame (block) which is reflected in accordance with the advertising site's content. Its main goal is to bring in more target customers and boost sales for already established businesses. Transport-related advertising is a contemporary and varied form of marketing. Nowadays, almost any type of vehicle, including a car, tram, trolley bus, bus, train, airplane, and even a rocket carrier, can have advertising placed on its side.

Conclusion: A major part of raising people's awareness of anything that might be important to them is through advertising. The methods of production and presentation of advertisements have undergone numerous changes over the course of their long history. It is crucial for newcomers and students of advertising to be aware of the history of advertising in Egypt, the UK, and Belarus in order to comprehend how changes have

progressed over time and what potential future changes there may be. The current development of technologies gives advertisers the chance to broadcast their shows more freely. Having three countries (Egypt, the UK, and Belarus) in my study situated in different parts of world gave me a unique chance to conduct study and to answer the question who invented the art of advertising and to see how our cultures differentiate related to an overview of advertising through historical, legal, and literature perspective. In some respects these countries are similar, in others they are different. I conclude that in advertising in these three countries a big progress happened over the recent years. By the beginning of the 21st Century, a big role was played for using technology in advertising. Online advertising, which uses the Internet to promote products and services to audiences, allows people in these countries to find, reach, and engage people who are likely to be interested in your advertising and offers the audience information, so you can focus your efforts effectively. Legal overview is more or less the same in all of these countries, the legal side concentrates on the values, cultural, and moral concepts of the given countries.

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